

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Edinburgh Futures Institute

Inclusive Futures for Digital Research Infrastructures: Scenarios and Impacts on User Ecosystems

Authors: Steven Earl, Pushpi Bagchi, Kam Chan, Kyle Morrison

Partners:

Hartree Centre

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings from a series of foresight workshops exploring how different models of federated Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) could shape participation across user communities. The purpose of the workshop series was to understand what conditions need to be considered to support more inclusive futures for federated infrastructure.

The workshop series consisted of three sessions held in London, Daresbury, and Edinburgh. In each session, participants worked collaboratively to create alternative scenarios for the future of federated infrastructure, drawing on research outputs from the project. They explored the consequences of these scenarios for three user archetypes: active users (already embedded within infrastructure systems), potential users (who could benefit from participation but face barriers to entry), and inactive users (currently excluded or disconnected from infrastructure ecosystems). This scenario-impact approach allowed participants to explore how different governance arrangements, infrastructure coordination models, and epistemic assumptions influence who can participate in federated infrastructures and on what terms.

Across all futures scenario landscapes generated, inclusive federated infrastructure depends less on technology choices alone. They depend more on how governance power, interoperability arrangements, capability development pathways, and representation instruments are designed and sustained. While centralised approaches support coordination, accountability, and national-scale capability, more distributed approaches support flexibility, experimentation, and community responsiveness. Neither approach guarantees inclusion as participation depends on the availability of clear entry pathways, trusted governance conditions, sustained skills development, and navigable connections between services across the infrastructure ecosystem.

The workshops also identified that epistemic pluralism (the ability of infrastructure to support multiple knowledge traditions, disciplines, and methodological approaches) is a shared priority across user communities. Achieving pluralism requires active support through translation mechanisms, representation in governance structures, and interoperability frameworks that connect diverse infrastructures without enforcing premature convergence.

Across all user types, participation was shaped less by infrastructure availability and more by governance clarity, institutional alignment, capability readiness, and access to trusted participation pathways. Smaller organisations, emerging disciplines, and communities currently outside the infrastructure ecosystem remain at risk of exclusion across all scenario landscapes and unless deliberate interventions are made to support representation, onboarding, and long-term capability-building.

The findings suggest that decisions about federated infrastructure design are decisions about participation. The scenarios developed are not forecasts, themselves, but should

be used as structured tools that show how different infrastructure choices shape inclusion. They highlight the importance of investing not only in infrastructure systems but also in the governance arrangements, skills development, interoperability coordination, and engagement pathways required to make federation usable across diverse research communities.

Participants identified priority areas for resourcing and investing that strengthen participation independent of infrastructure approach or model, these include: long-term skills and training provision, clear and navigable entry pathways into federation, interoperability frameworks across providers and domains, governance participation and representation mechanisms, and translation and support capacity for diverse research communities.

The key insights surfaced from across the workshop series exercises, are summarised below:

Key insights from workshop series:

- Inclusive federated infrastructure futures are shaped more by governance design than by technology choices alone.
- Participation across all user groups depends on clear entry pathways, trusted governance conditions, interoperability between services, and sustained capability development.
- Centralised infrastructure models improve coordination, accountability, and national-scale capability but can reduce flexibility and widen participation thresholds.
- Distributed infrastructure models support experimentation, autonomy, and community responsiveness but increase navigation complexity and coordination overhead.
- Epistemic pluralism is a shared priority across workshop participants and requires active support through translation mechanisms, representation in governance, and interoperable infrastructure frameworks.
- Smaller organisations, emerging disciplines, and communities outside the current infrastructure ecosystem remain at risk of exclusion across all scenario futures without targeted support.
- Skills, training, and institutional capability-building emerged as the most consistent participation enabler across all scenarios, user archetypes, and workshop participants' discussions.
- Infrastructure decisions create long-term path dependencies that shape who can participate and how research is conducted over time.
- Economic suitability and sustainability give confidence and shape user expectations. Including incentive structures (funding, training) and policy priorities and directions.

These cross-cutting insights surface strategic considerations for infrastructure design and coordination. The following discussion points are areas that need to be resolved to influence inclusive participation across future federation models.

Critical discussion points for strategic considerations:

- Establishing governance arrangements as a primary infrastructure design, not a secondary implementation issue.
- Investment in onboarding pathways, training provision, and capability-building as core infrastructure components not optional support activities.
- Design participation pathways that support communities currently outside the Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) active user ecosystem, on terms suitable for potential and inactive users.
- Prioritise interoperability coordination across provisions to ensure federation remains usable across institutions and disciplines.
- Support epistemic pluralism through representation mechanisms, translation activities, and potentially modular infrastructure architectures.
- Balance national coordination with community-level autonomy to avoid creating participation thresholds that exclude smaller organisations.
- Develop sustainable economic and incentive models that support long-term participation rather than episodic engagement.
- Ensure infrastructure strategy recognises and actively manages trade-offs between coordination, flexibility, inclusion, and scalability.

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Introduction

A series of three foresight workshops were held in London at University College London (UCL), Daresbury at Hartree Centre, and in Edinburgh at Edinburgh Futures Institute (EFI) to capture participants' current views, assumptions, and concerns around federation, while creating space to collectively imagine and shape more preferable futures for federated DRIs. Participants were a mix of academic researchers, industry practitioners, and service providers. The series asked participants to consider two structural dimensions of federated DRIs that shape questions of inclusion: how power should be distributed across the federation, and what kinds of knowledge and practice should it accommodate.

Participants were asked to establish and explore futures scenarios that different approaches to federated DRIs could take and identify how these may affect different user communities. The aim was to help identify practical considerations for how DRIs could be more inclusive, what an ethical approach to change could be, and the types of support and culture that is needed to establish associated inclusive futures.

Each workshop followed three phases: immersion in research outputs from earlier work packages (WP1); scenario development exploring alternative futures for federated DRIs; and assessment of how these scenarios would affect different user communities to inform recommendations for more inclusive infrastructure futures. This approach ensured that the needs of Active, Potential, and Inactive users were embedded throughout the process and provided a structured way to examine how different federation arrangements may shape participation across the research ecosystem.

Outputs from each of the exercises across all three workshops informed the insights, and considerations below:

- Inclusive federated infrastructure futures are shaped more by governance design than by technology choices alone.
- Participation across all user groups depends on clear entry pathways, trusted governance conditions, interoperability between services, and sustained capability development.
- Centralised infrastructure models improve coordination, accountability, and national-scale capability but can reduce flexibility and widen participation thresholds.
- Distributed infrastructure models support experimentation, autonomy, and community responsiveness but increase navigation complexity and coordination overhead.
- Epistemic pluralism is a shared priority across workshop participants and requires active support through translation mechanisms, representation in governance, and interoperable infrastructure frameworks.

- Smaller organisations, emerging disciplines, and communities outside the current infrastructure ecosystem remain at risk of exclusion across all scenario futures without targeted support.
- Skills, training, and institutional capability-building emerged as the most consistent participation enabler across all scenarios, user archetypes, and workshop participants discussions.
- Infrastructure decisions create long-term path dependencies that shape who can participate and how research is conducted over time.
- Economic suitability and sustainability give confidence and shape user expectations. Including incentive structures (funding, training) and policy priorities and directions.

The structure of the report focuses on each of the four exercises undertaken across the workshop series: Exercise 1- User Archetypes within the DRIs Ecosystem; Exercise 2 - Future Scenarios of DRIs; Exercise 3 - Consequences and Impacts of the Scenarios on Users; and Exercise 4 - Workshop Participants' Reflections and Recommendations. The report concludes by summarising the key insights from across all exercises. Each section introduces the exercise, summarises the associated outputs, and highlights relevant considerations. Detailed summaries of each exercise are available in the Appendices.

User Archetypes – Exercise 1

Exercise 1 focused on developing well-defined user archetypes for DRIs. This established a shared reference point for the subsequent futures scenario development (Exercises 2 and 3) and to ground the whole process in user-centred considerations.

Workshop participants were presented with the key findings from the survey, interviews, and scoping review (WP1) that emphasised three key user types. Active Users, Potential Users, and Inactive Users and are defined as:

- Active Users: Currently engaged with federated systems and research infrastructure
- Potential Users: Could benefit from but not yet participating in federation
- Inactive Users: Disengaged or excluded from federated systems

Participants were invited to reflect on and refine these user archetypes; who they are, their potential gains from federation, potential losses, and current frustrations. A generalised overview from across all workshops can be seen in the table below, while a detailed version of users identified from each workshop can be found in Appendix A.

User Archetype	Who they are	Key Insights / Needs / Frustrations
Active User	HPC researchers, clinical data researchers, GLAM researchers, research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Want interoperability and access to more datasets/compute

	infrastructure staff, platform operators, institutional infrastructure teams, funded infrastructure users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerned about loss of autonomy and local control • Frustrated by fragmented access pathways and coordination gaps • Need to demonstrate value beyond existing workflows to their organisation • Managing governance complexity and competing standards
Potential User	Early-career researchers, interdisciplinary researchers, bioscience researchers, health researchers, moving toward compute, collaborative research teams, applied/industry-linked researchers, education users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interested but unsure how to enter systems • Need training, onboarding, and clearer entry points • Want access to tools, datasets, and collaboration opportunities • Concerned about learning curve and workflow disruption • Frustrated by low discoverability and unclear value proposition
Inactive User	SMEs and startups, financial/regulatory sector organisations, voluntary/community sector, non-HPC researchers, small museums/archives, cloud-dependent organisations,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often unclear how federation applies to them and its relevance • Concerned about governance, IP, compliance, and trust • Limited technical capacity or resources to engage • Perceive systems as complex or bureaucratic • Frustrated by unclear pathways, relevance, and return on effort

The participants used the user archetypes in Exercise 3, to analysis the impacts of the futures scenarios developed in Exercise 2.

Futures Scenarios of Federated DRIs – Exercise 2

Futures scenarios are structured narratives of plausible alternative futures. They are used to help explore how different combinations of dynamics, decisions, governance models, technologies and institutional arrangements may shape future infrastructure and related ecosystems. Scenario methods are useful when uncertainty is high and when infrastructure choices made today may create long-term path dependencies.

In this project, scenarios were used to explore how different relationships between epistemic cultures, how knowledge is produced, inclusive, and validated, and infrastructure power, who makes decisions about standards, systems, and access as well as autonomy within this infrastructure. The tensions generated by these dimensions were used to create alternative future scenarios that provide insights into decision-making today.

The scenario landscapes are structured around two key dimensions:

1. Epistemic culture: Whether federated research infrastructures support homogenised or plural epistemic cultures
2. Infrastructure power: Whether infrastructure power is centralised or distributed

Future Scenario landscape archetypes

These dimensions can be used as two axes that produce four distinct futures scenario landscapes, seen in Figure 1. Where inside each scenario there is a unique approach to infrastructure coordination, practices, systems and logics, that provide insight into the conditions needed for them to operate and to invest in. It is not intended to be used as a choice between the scenarios but as way of using the insights to generate an approach that is suitable and sustainable. Participants of the three workshops were asked to establish scenarios within these dimensions generating 60 scenarios in total.

The scenarios produced were clustered together and four consistent future landscape archetypes were identified. Several sub-archetypes were identified within each of the future landscapes focused on different aspects of the broader scenario landscape but were consistent within. Each landscape established different approaches to standards, operating environments, models, and interoperability frameworks. These choices shaped who could participate, which methods and approaches were supported, how disciplines and organisations collaborated, how effectively systems responded to emerging challenges, and how resilient they remained over time. This involved balancing trade-offs between coordination and diversity, autonomy and interoperability, strategic capability and local flexibility, and investment in support infrastructure and long-term planning. The established scenarios are later used in Exercise 3 to help provide insights into how decisions will affect users generated Exercise 1.

Figure 1- Four future (2040) landscape archetypes generated from across all workshops

Short overviews of scenarios

Using the outputs of the workshops short narratives for each scenario have been produced. These are described below and generalised from across all three workshops, there are distinct sub-narratives within these, that are described in Appendix B.

Future Scenario Landscape A - The Managed Knowledge Machine

(Homogenised epistemic culture + Centralised power)

Infrastructure is centrally coordinated and based on a dominant set of standards, workflows, and computational expectations. Systems are efficient, predictable, and scalable, but alternative approaches and change is harder to support. Infrastructure decisions can create strong dependencies on chosen architectures, platforms, or vendors.

<p>Key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> centrally coordinated research infrastructure shared standards, workflows, and computational environments alignment with national priorities or platform ecosystems 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> high efficiency and scalability strong coordination across institutions reliable security and compliance frameworks
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • predictable and secure infrastructure environments • limited flexibility outside approved tools and pipelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supports large-scale mission-oriented science <p>Risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduced epistemic diversity • dependence on central infrastructure providers or vendors • limited support for unconventional research approaches • reduced long-term infrastructure flexibility and resilience
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Future Scenario Landscape B - The Standardised Federation

(Homogenised epistemic culture + Distributed power)

Governance is distributed across institutions and communities, but shared technical standards, technology pipelines, and funding incentives gradually produce convergence across the system. The infrastructure is perceived to be plural and decentralised, and knowledge production becomes aligned around similar methods and architectures.

<p>Key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • governance shared across institutions and research communities • interoperability through common standards and protocols • widespread use of shared AI stacks and infrastructure layers • convergence shaped by funding, procurement, and compatibility needs • collaboration enabled through distributed but aligned systems 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strong interoperability across organisations • scalable collaboration across institutional networks • legitimacy through distributed governance participation • efficient reuse of shared infrastructure components <p>Risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gradual convergence of research practices over time • hidden dependencies on shared infrastructure layers • difficulty identifying emerging monocultures early • reduced flexibility for alternative methodological approaches
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Future Scenario Landscape C - The Managed Plural Commons

(Plural epistemic cultures + Centralised power)

Multiple knowledge traditions are recognised and supported within shared infrastructures coordinated by central organisations. Diversity is visible and

institutionally supported, but participation often depends on adapting to shared frameworks and interoperability requirements.

<p>Key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • central coordination of shared infrastructure frameworks • explicit recognition of multiple knowledge traditions • structured interoperability across disciplines and communities • representation-based governance arrangements • shared platforms supporting diverse research approaches 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enables collaboration across diverse knowledge communities • supports inclusion of disciplinary and non-traditional expertise • maintains interoperability at national scale • strengthens coordination across infrastructure investments <p>Risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pluralism dependent on continued central commitment • translation burdens for some communities • concentration of architectural decision-making power • risk of diversity being curated rather than fully self-determined
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Future Scenario Landscape D - The Distributed Plural Commons

(Plural epistemic cultures + Distributed power)

Communities shape their own infrastructures, standards, and research practices. Innovation and experimentation increase, but coordination across systems becomes more complex and must be negotiated rather than assumed.

<p>Key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • community-led infrastructure governance • diverse tools, standards, and workflows across domains • federated collaboration between independent research ecosystems • experimentation-driven innovation environments • lightweight interoperability negotiated between communities 	<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high levels of experimentation and innovation • strong local autonomy and adaptability • supports diverse disciplinary and community needs • reduces dependency on single infrastructure providers <p>Risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fragmented infrastructure ecosystems • reduced interoperability across domains • duplication of effort and investment • weaker coordination for large-scale national or international challenges
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Key Learnings from the Scenario Landscapes and Scenarios

Across all the scenario and key archetype landscapes. Common patterns were emphasised in different configurations such as responsibilities on how a federation organises themselves and their infrastructure around standards, interoperability, compute access, translation of offers, funding pathways and engagement models. All are dependent on available resources, capacity, and capability to maintain these. However, depending on how the federation approached infrastructure power, the epistemic cultures emerged differently.

Infrastructure Power (Centralised – Distributed)

Typically, the landscapes showed that centralised power (**A** and **C**) shared features around infrastructure coherence, strong interoperability, clearer accountability structures, easier national-scale coordination and potential to align to larger policy missions or agendas. **A** typically achieving these through methods, and **C** through coordination approaches, meaning that governance can support pluralism and inclusion if designed to do so.

Landscapes that showed more emphasis on distributed power (**B** and **D**) shared more institutional/user autonomy, local control, community-led evolution, and flexible experimentation environments. **B** typically doing this through alignment of practices, and **D** through experimentation and associated documentation. Again infrastructure design only enables pluralism and inclusion if embedded in the infrastructure approach.

Epistemic cultures (Homogenised – Plural)

The homogenised epistemic cultures landscapes (**A** and **B**) surfaced more shared workflows and validation expectations, easier interoperability, scalable collaboration and reproducibility environments. Suggesting choices on infrastructure limits or expands inclusion.

Finally, landscapes that focused more on plural epistemic cultures (**C** and **D**), showed more recognition of multiple knowledge/domain needs, broader interdisciplinary collaboration potential, community participation pathways, and support diverse methodological approaches. However, the breadth of the portfolio focus will be based on resources, maintaining access pathways, and coordination.

Across all scenarios

The four futures landscape archetypes emphasised that inclusive futures within research infrastructure are shaped less by technology choices and more by how governance power and epistemic assumptions interact.

The scenarios demonstrate that infrastructure decisions determine not only how research is conducted, but also who can (and gets to) participate, what methods are

supported, and how adaptable the system remains over time. Some key themes were identified from across all the scenarios:

Infrastructure governance shapes knowledge production

The scenarios show that infrastructure is not neutral. Decisions about standards, compute environments, interoperability layers, access mechanisms, and metadata expectations actively shape what kinds of research become visible, fundable, and scalable.

Centralised systems can strengthen coordination. Distributed systems can strengthen experimentation. Neither guarantees diversity on their own, and there is opportunity to establish what is useful for different activities and services.

Epistemic diversity depends on infrastructure architecture

Supporting multiple knowledge traditions requires: translation layers, modular architectures, documentation interoperability, training systems, governance representation. Without these, pluralism may be symbolic rather than valued or operational. Several scenarios demonstrate that inclusion does not automatically produce epistemic diversity, where access can increase while methodological diversity declines.

Homogenisation can emerge with or without central control

A key insight across scenario landscapes **A** and **B** is that “monocultures” form in two distinct ways. Through explicit central coordination (**A**) and through distributed alignment around shared standards, infrastructure stacks, or incentives (**B**). This means that convergence can occur even when governance appears decentralised.

Pluralism increases innovation, but needs additional coordination and scaffolding

D surfaced that plural epistemic ecosystems support experimentation, enable adaptation, and encourage community-led infrastructure evolution. But the need of a federated approach would need to support, coordinate and scaffold interoperability, and duplication. Pluralism in these cultures is more focused on the coordination and scaffolding to enable connectivity.

Central coordination can enable pluralism

C shows that central governance does not automatically produce monoculture. Instead, central actors can: stabilise interoperability, fund translation mechanisms, support diverse participation pathways, and maintain infrastructure coherence across domains. This is dependent and conditional on continued institutional commitment.

Infrastructure decisions create long-term path dependencies

Across landscapes **A**, **B**, and **C** especially, scenarios show that early choices about: compute architectures, vendor ecosystems, metadata standards, and federation layers all shape future research capability for the long term. Once established, infrastructure logics are difficult to reverse.

Scenario consequences on user archetypes – Exercise 3

Exercise 3 focused on the consequences of the futures scenarios on the user archetypes generating in Exercise 1. This is known as wind-tunnelling or stress-testing, where the implications of each scenario are examined across the different user types. This process involves identifying the common patterns of needs, barriers, and opportunities within and across each user group, while generating insights into how each scenario may impact all users. The two tables below show brief overviews of the insights generated, and the common patterns across all scenarios for each user type. There is a more detailed version of this in Appendix C. Common insights relevant to all users are discussed and highlighted

User type	Scenario A	Scenario B	Scenario C	Scenario D
Active Users	Alignment vs autonomy - strengthens coordination and standardisation for active users but reduces flexibility and control over tools, workflows, and data.	Autonomy vs coordination - increases provider choice and specialist control but reduces interoperability and coordination across the ecosystem.	Diversity vs scalability - supports experimentation and specialist collaboration but increases coordination effort and risks limiting experimentation as systems scale.	Flexibility vs coordination overhead - supports innovation and alignment with research needs but increases interoperability demands and competition for shared infrastructure capacity.
Potential Users	Clarity vs conditional inclusion - makes participation pathways clearer and easier to navigate but increases reliance on central systems and risks excluding organisations that do not meet entry conditions.	Incremental entry vs navigation complexity - enables gradual entry through local and specialised services but creates navigation challenges and uneven participation without strong interoperability.	Automation vs skills and trust barriers - supports collaboration through shared standards and automation but makes participation more dependent on digital literacy, governance alignment, and trust in	Choice vs navigation complexity/reliability increases service choice and alignment with user needs but raises navigation complexity, literacy requirements, and uncertainty around reliability and trusted participation.

			infrastructure systems.	
Inactive Users	<p>Certainty vs institutional dependence - creates a more predictable and policy-aligned infrastructure environment but increases reliance on government direction and advantages larger organisations over smaller participants.</p>	<p>Resilience vs entry complexity - improves accountability and service resilience through provider plurality but increases coordination complexity and participation barriers without clear entry pathways.</p>	<p>Mobility vs representation and support capacity- supports institutional mobility and multiple adoption pathways but requires strong representation mechanisms and technical support to enable participation from smaller communities.</p>	<p>Alignment flexibility vs governance clarity and communication barriers - allows organisations to shape participation around their needs but increases uncertainty about accountability, shared vocabulary, and participation pathways for smaller communities.</p>

Common patterns and insights can be identified for each user, based on their perspective responses to each scenario:

User type	Insights from across all scenarios that effect each user group
Active Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • innovation depends on balancing coordination with flexibility • interoperability is essential for collaboration at scale • governance shapes both access and methodological autonomy • provider diversity improves resilience but increases coordination effort • distributed systems increase competition for shared resources • platform dependence and vendor lock-in remain ongoing concerns • infrastructure diversity increases technical workload • specialist infrastructures support communities but risk ecosystem fragmentation
Potential Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • clear entry pathways determine whether participation is possible • greater provider choice increases opportunity but complicates navigation • governance and data rules shape willingness to participate • digital literacy and onboarding support are essential participation conditions • standardisation supports collaboration but may reduce flexibility • smaller organisations remain at risk of exclusion without targeted support • interoperability is critical in distributed infrastructure environments • local and education-based entry points support gradual engagement
Inactive Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • governance clarity determines whether participation feels possible • institutional alignment matters more than technical access • smaller and emerging communities remain at risk of exclusion

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• skills pipelines and capability-building shape long-term participation• greater provider choice increases flexibility but also complexity• policy direction strongly shapes participation expectations• representation in governance is essential for engagement• stability and continuity matter more than optimisation or experimentation |
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Common insights from across all users

Insights across all user types and scenarios suggest that inclusion and participation depend less on the availability of infrastructure and more on governance clarity, capability support, interoperability, representation, and clear pathways into the ecosystem. These insights can be summarised as:

- 1. Governance clarity determines whether users can participate** - clear accountability, decision-making structures, and data rules all shape participation confidence.
- 2. Institutional alignment matters more than technical access** - does infrastructures fit organisational priorities, workflows, and funding environments.
- 3. Skills and training pathways are essential for participation** - capability-building consistently emerges as a prerequisite for adoption across all futures.
- 4. More provider choice increases flexibility, but also complexity** - distributed infrastructures improve resilience but make participation harder to navigate.
- 5. Representation gaps persist across all scenarios** - smaller organisations, emerging disciplines, and under-represented communities remain at risk of exclusion without deliberate interventions.
- 6. Interoperability is critical for a usable infrastructure ecosystem** - participation improves when systems connect smoothly across providers and domains.
- 7. Policy direction strongly shapes participation expectations** - users consistently interpret infrastructure futures as shaped by national strategy and governance priorities.
- 8. Clear navigation pathways are necessary across all infrastructure models** - users need to understand where to start, how services connect, and how to move between systems.
- 9. All scenarios reflect a trade-off between coordination and flexibility** - coordination improves clarity and stability, while more flexibility improves innovation and local alignment.

Participant Positioning: Dialogue on Power and Epistemic Culture – Exercise 4

The workshop series asked participants to consider two structural dimensions of federated DRI that shape questions of inclusion: how power should be distributed across the federation, and what kinds of knowledge and practice it should accommodate. In exercise 4 invited participants were asked to indicate where federated infrastructures are positioned *today* on both axes, and based on their scenarios and considerations through the workshop where DRIs should aim to be by 2040. The following charts present their responses across all three cohorts.

Perceived current state of federated infrastructures (Q3a: Power; Q3b: Epistemic Culture). Responses clustered toward centralisation and, notably, showed a bimodal split on epistemic culture; suggesting participants hold genuinely divergent views of the current landscape.

Desired future positioning by 2040 upon scenario development (Q3c: Power; Q3d: Epistemic Culture), following the scenario exercise. Responses on epistemic culture converge towards (plural) across all three cohorts. Responses on power distribution remain spread.

Desired future positioning by 2040 post scenario analysis (Q4b: Power; Q4c: Epistemic Culture), following the scenario analysis exercise. Responses on epistemic culture converge strongly at +4/+5 (plural) across all three cohorts. Responses on power distribution remain spread, clustering modestly around 0 to +2.

Taken together, these charts point to an asymmetry in participant priorities. There is a strong cross-cohort consensus that NFCS should move toward epistemic pluralism, and this consensus strengthened after participants worked through how different scenarios affect distinct user types.

The perception on power distribution is more contested: responses remained spread across the scale, with no dominant position. This suggests that epistemic inclusion is a stable shared value, while questions of centralisation versus decentralisation are treated as contingent, dependent on institutional context, user type, and governance design. This finding also informs the themes that follow.

Thematic Insights

The following thematic clusters have been drawn from two questions asked to the participants:

1. 4a) What surprised you most in your scenario assessment?
2. 4d) Share one recommendation for building more inclusive federated futures.

Across three workshop cohorts, London, Daresbury, and Edinburgh, participant responses to open-ended scenario questions converged around five interconnected themes. These themes are presented below, each with a summary of the key concern, illustrative participant quotes, and a recommendation to consider at the policy roundtable.

Theme 1: The Scope and Complexity of ‘Federation’

The scope and complexity of ‘federation’ is not shared, which creates a structural barrier. Participants across all three cohorts were struck by the extent to which fundamental terms, federation, High performance computing (HPC), infrastructure, carry different meanings depending on who is in the room.

This is not a communications problem. Divergent understandings of what federation means produce different assumptions about who benefits, who makes decisions, or what success looks like. Facilitator notes from the Daresbury session underlined this: "the term HPC means different things to different people," and participants entered the scenario exercises with distinct, often divergent baseline assumptions. Additionally, the poll data on current epistemic culture (Q3b) is also illustrative: responses split sharply between homogenised and plural, suggesting that participants do not share a baseline reading of where federated DRI currently sits. The absence of a shared vocabulary is not a precondition to be resolved before the 'real work' begins, it is itself a governance problem.

Illustrative Responses and Facilitator Notes

- Diversity of understanding of what federated means. (London)
- Range of interpretations of the definitions. (London)
- The need for clear common terms. (Daresbury)
- The general level of consistency of the perspectives on the scenarios that we arrived at. (Edinburgh noting surprise at the degree of convergence despite starting from different places)

Recommendations for considerations

There is a need to map the landscape of meanings/interpretations attached to federation, compute, and infrastructure across different user communities. Rather than a glossary exercise, it would be a systematic effort to surface whose definitions currently dominate governance design, and whose are marginalised. Outputs might include a stakeholder-centric lexicon co-produced with diverse communities, and governance guidance on managing definitional plurality without enforcing premature convergence.

Theme 2: Skills and Capacity Gaps

The most repeated single recommendation from participants was, in various forms, regarding skills. A lack of skills and capacity gaps were perceived as a key barrier to inclusion, not access to infrastructure. Participants recognised that even a well-designed federated infrastructure is functionally inaccessible to communities that lack the capacity to engage with it. This includes a) awareness of what is available, b) technical proficiency to use it, and c) institutional support to sustain that engagement over time. Facilitator notes from the Daresbury session captured the structural dimension of this clearly: "*There is a desperate need for upskilling across all users*", but also the circular problem that "*until we know what the system looks like, we don't know what training materials to build*". Participants at Edinburgh connected this to funding: skills development needs long-term, core resourcing, not episodic project support.

Illustrative Responses and Facilitator Notes

- TRAINING, TRAINING, TRAINING. (Edinburgh)
- People and skills are the most important foundation. (London)
- Funding for skills development (to use FDRI and realise opportunities. (Daresbury)

- Accreditation training for interacting with the NFCS, to have a distributed network of specialists that can help in hands-on situations. (London)
- A lot of the funding going into this area in the last 20 years has been very episodic. How does the community benefit, training, open resource, service wrapper, core/long-term funding recommendation? Gives the community comfort that there will be money coming, so that knowledge doesn't get lost. (Edinburgh Facilitators' Note)

Recommendation for considerations

There is a need for a focus on skills and capacity, which should be prioritised, with a specific emphasis on distributed, community-based models rather than centralised training provision. This should include mapping skills gaps across Active, Inactive, and Potential User communities; developing adaptable training resources (including 'service wrappers' that reduce technical barriers to entry); and making a strong case for long-term, sustained funding for capacity development as a core infrastructure cost that is maintained long term.

Consideration should also be given to communities that currently sit entirely outside the DRI ecosystem and require foundational outreach before training is even relevant.

Theme 3: Governance

Participants consistently identified governance, not technology, as the primary lever for inclusion or exclusion. Scenario exercises revealed that the same technical infrastructure can produce radically different outcomes depending on how decisions are made, who has a voice, and how power is distributed. This was a key insight for many participants: that the configuration of governance shapes user experience as fundamentally as the configuration of compute.

Facilitator notes from multiple sessions highlighted the tension between centralisation (which enables coordination, funding leverage, and accountability) and distribution (which enables responsiveness to diverse community needs). Several participants pointed to the risk of defaulting to current power arrangements, what one facilitator note called “sleepwalking into the future.” Governance design is a decisive variable which appears under-theorised.

The previous charts reinforce this finding: participants did not converge on a preferred power distribution, but they did converge strongly on the need for epistemic pluralism. Governance frameworks should be designed to accommodate that asymmetry.

Illustrative Responses and Facilitator Notes

- Centralised control can allow decisions which even disenfranchise mainstream existing users. E.g., Archer shutdown. (London)
- In the context of 2040, a lot of analytics will likely be automated. So we need centralisation to oversee governance. You could have community guards who keep changing to ensure diversity of perspectives. (Daresbury Facilitator Note)
- A governing body should be like a lighthouse — inspire people and educate/enable them rather than forcing people to choose sides. Need to interest people from different backgrounds and inspire a community practice. (Edinburgh Facilitator Note)

- We need to get away from the current notion of power, in terms of who owns a particular system and pivot it to how many are involved. (Edinburgh Facilitator Note)
- Radical inclusion when designing governance (include not only voices of users and providers but also of the public), the common good. (Edinburgh)

Recommendation for considerations

Governance design should proceed on the principle that no single model, centralised or distributed, is inherently inclusive. There is a potential to develop governance frameworks that are: adaptive (able to distribute power along different dimensions depending on context); participatory (built with input from non-traditional and currently excluded communities); and accountable (with clear mechanisms for rotation, review, and challenge). Participants at Daresbury suggested drawing on international examples of federated governance (Dare UK, Xroad, and others) and should avoid reproducing existing power asymmetries by assuming active users are the primary constituency.

Theme 4: Economic Models and Incentive Structures

Summary

Participants raised persistent concerns about the economic logics shaping federated infrastructure: who funds it, what they expect in return, and how that shapes access. The question of where money or funding comes from, government, industry, institutions, or some hybrid, was identified as a governance question as much as a financial one. Participants at Daresbury in particular noted the risk of industry capture: “accepting that Big Tech is likely going to take over.” Others noted that funding scarcity forces prioritisation decisions that are rarely made explicit or deliberated. Facilitator notes from the Daresbury session pointed to the structural consequence: “if you're not making an impact, you're not getting funding, vs if you're not dependent on the funder, you can make your own impact.”

Illustrative Participant Quotes

- Economic model. (Daresbury, identified as a key surprise of doing the scenario analysis)
- There is a finite pot of money, pick your focus early; include users early in the decision-making/adoption process. (Daresbury Facilitator Note)
- Clear incentives for adoption (London)
- Sustainability of DRIs through various support systems, or lack of those (Edinburgh)
- Organisations need a good reason to give up their resources — it needs to be a two-way relationship." (Daresbury Facilitator Note)
- Does the money come from industry? Monetised through exploitation. We are driven by data; we are more driven by money." (Daresbury Facilitator Note)

Recommendation for considerations

Economic models and sustainability should map the funding assumptions currently embedded in federated DRI design, and their implications for inclusion. It should examine which user communities are legible as ‘impactful’ within current funding logics; how incentive structures can be designed to support two-way

relationships between infrastructure providers and communities; and what a sustainable, non-episodic funding model for inclusive DRIs would look like.

Theme 5: Communities Outside the Current Ecosystem

Summary

A recurring concern across workshops was the risk of designing for existing users, those already visible, already articulate, already inside the infrastructure. Participants repeatedly noted that the communities most likely to benefit from a more inclusive federated DRI are precisely those least likely to turn up to a workshop, respond to a survey, or know what 'HPC' means.

Facilitator notes from Hartree captured this tension: "we also need to build a mindset where people don't think that their problems are just their own", and "try to reach audiences you don't know much about. They may surprise you."

Participants highlighted specific under-served groups: non-traditional HPC users, industry and SMEs, social science and humanities communities, and potential users who currently have no relationship with DRI at all.

Illustrative Participant Quotes

- Try to reach audiences you don't know much about. They may surprise you. (London)
- DRI may not be for everyone, but by 2040 it may be better possible for anyone to participate in the DRI. (Daresbury)
- Older systems were driven by compute ability; current systems are driven by data, this creates possibility for non-traditional users, so we need to consider diverse users. (Daresbury Facilitator Note)
- Amplify the value, and collaborate, with the social sciences and the humanities." (Edinburgh Facilitator Note)
- Find out which communities can make use of it. And realise that as technology changes, differing communities may be on boardable. (Daresbury)
- Creating an effective communication environment to foster effective collaboration across a federated environment, while also being wary of distributed systems and their respective cultures. (Daresbury)

Recommendation for considerations

Community engagement and outreach should prioritise communities currently outside the DRI ecosystem, not those already within it.

This might involve developing a typology of 'potential users' beyond the standard active/inactive distinction; mapping where non-traditional communities currently meet their compute and data needs, and on what terms; and co-designing engagement strategies with those communities rather than retrofitting existing DRI communications. This work should also consider how case studies and demonstrators can make the value of DRI legible to communities for whom current framing is opaque or alienating.

Conclusions – insights, and considerations for DRIs

Across all exercises in the workshop series, a consistent set of themes emerged about the structural conditions required to support inclusive futures for federated Digital Research Infrastructure. These findings show that participation depends less on infrastructure availability alone and more on how governance, interoperability, capability development, representation, and entry pathways are designed and sustained across the federation. The considerations presented below draw together these cross-cutting insights to support strategic discussion on how DRIs can position itself to enable inclusive participation across diverse research communities.

1. Coordination vs flexibility

Stronger coordination can improve clarity, interoperability, accountability, and scale, but may reduce autonomy, experimentation, and responsiveness to diverse needs.

2. Inclusion depends on more than access

Across user archetypes, participation is not mainly about whether infrastructure exists, but whether people can understand it, trust it, navigate it, and see themselves reflected in it.

3. Governance is a core design consideration

Governance shapes who participates, whose knowledge counts, how standards are set, and whether pluralism is real or symbolic.

4. Pluralism needs active support

Pluralism needs scaffolding: translation, representation, interoperability, training, and support. It rarely happens automatically or “naturally”

5. Capability-building is foundational

Skills, onboarding, support, and long-term capacity are essential implying that infrastructure investment without people investment will reproduce exclusion.

6. Distributed systems create opportunity and complexity at the same time

More providers, more autonomy, and more local choice can improve resilience and alignment, but also make systems harder to navigate, govern, and connect.

7. Smaller and less visible communities remain structurally vulnerable

Across scenarios and user types, under-represented, smaller, emerging, or less well-resourced communities remain at risk unless inclusion is deliberately designed in.

These tensions lend to critical questions that need strategic consideration:

1. What should NFCS coordinate centrally, and what should it deliberately leave distributed?

2. How can NFCS support epistemic pluralism without making participation too complex to navigate?
3. Who is not currently in the room, and what would have to change for them to participate meaningfully?
4. What should take priority when they come into conflict: interoperability, autonomy, inclusion, or efficiency?
5. What kinds of governance arrangements make under-represented communities visible in real decision-making?
6. What long-term investments in skills, support, and representation are necessary for user types for inclusive federation is to be credible?

Appendices

Appendix A - User archetypes identified across all workshops

Active User Archetypes

Workshop 1				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Health Data & Clinical Research Users	Clinical staff, researchers, and TRE/SDE providers working within health data ecosystems.	Greater access to diverse datasets, improved health outcomes, and the ability to link and reuse data across systems.	Privacy and security risks, increased governance requirements, and loss of control over sensitive data.	Lack of coordination, limited transparency, and difficulty accessing and linking datasets across systems.
GLAM & Cultural Research Users	Researchers, curators, and institutions in galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM), including cultural data stewards.	Ability to connect collections (e.g., through a common platform/interface) and access to strategic support for shared research missions.	Loss of control over data and infrastructure, dependence on external systems, and concerns over trust in providers.	Lack of resources and expertise, centralised control concerns, and trust issues in data and systems.
Research Infrastructure & Technical Professionals	Research software engineers, infrastructure specialists, and HPC community members supporting systems and users.	Improved interoperability, efficiency, and consistency across systems. Better utilisation of infrastructure and support for users.	Loss of autonomy, reduced flexibility, and constraints on innovation due to standardisation.	Managing change, maintaining control, balancing user needs vs. system constraints, and capacity limitations.
Academic & Specialist Researchers	Domain-specific researchers (e.g., physics) using specialised compute resources and established workflows.	Access to larger compute resources, improved user experience, and the ability to extend existing workflows.	Loss of agility and flexibility, and constraints imposed by federated frameworks.	System complexity, usability issues, and unclear benefits compared to existing approaches.
Public Sector & Federated System Users	NHS, voluntary sector, educators, and researchers engaging with or adjacent to federated systems.	Better resource sharing, improved data availability, and opportunities for collaboration and skill development.	Risk of exclusion if systems become mandatory, increased scrutiny, and potential inequities in access.	Lack of clarity on federation value, limited user involvement in design, and barriers to accessing systems.
Workshop 2				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations

Computational & HPC Researchers	Researchers, model developers, and platform users working in computational domains and using federated or HPC infrastructure.	Reduced duplication of effort, easier collaboration, and access to a wider range of compute resources and datasets.	Loss of autonomy over infrastructure and workflows and the need to adapt to shared systems.	Complex access processes, fragmented infrastructure, and time required to learn and navigate systems.
Institutional & Research Organisation Users	Research council departments, large institutions, and organisations managing or funding infrastructure (e.g., Hartree Centre).	Ability to pool resources, improve coordination, and increase efficiency across systems.	Reduced flexibility in local decision-making and increased dependency on federated governance.	Lack of transparency, coordination challenges, and difficulty aligning standards across systems.
Data-Driven & AI Researchers	Researchers working with large datasets, AI systems, and advanced analytics across domains.	Access to diverse datasets, improved compute capability, and opportunities for innovation and new insights.	Loss of control over data, risks around governance and security, and potential standardisation constraints.	Difficulty accessing high-quality data, fragmented systems, and barriers to integrating resources.
Research Infrastructure & Technical Staff	Technical professionals, infrastructure providers, and system operators managing HPC, data platforms, and services.	Greater interoperability, improved utilisation of resources, and the ability to support a broader user base.	Loss of flexibility in managing systems locally and increased complexity in coordination and integration.	Integration challenges, differing standards, and balancing performance, security, and usability.

Workshop 3				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
HPC & Advanced Compute Researchers	Researchers in HPC-heavy domains (physics, chemistry, AI) using large-scale simulations and compute-intensive workflows.	More seamless access to distributed compute resources, shared tools, and training. Ability to scale workloads and collaborate without duplicating infrastructure.	Reduced priority access to local systems, increased competition for resources, and loss of bespoke/optimised environments.	Queue times, complex access processes, data transfer challenges, and fragmented infrastructure.
Funded Research & Infrastructure Users	EPSRC/NERC-funded researchers and industrial R&D users working across multiple systems and compute environments.	Access to diverse compute systems, alternative resources, and improved workflows across infrastructures.	Governance complexity, lack of transparency in access, and reduced control over system choice.	Inconsistent access processes, unclear service layers, and difficulty navigating federated systems.
Heritage & Data Steward Community	Curators, archivists, and data stewards responsible for managing and sharing datasets across institutions.	Improved dataset discoverability, ability to connect collections, and access to tools for analysis and reuse.	Loss of control over data governance and processes, and pressure to standardise practices.	Limited resources, capacity constraints, and balancing preservation with accessibility.
HPC & Data Ecosystem Users	Established HPC users and large-scale compute communities (e.g., physics, chemistry) working within broader data ecosystems.	Easier access to appropriate resources, shared tools, and simplified access to multiple compute environments.	Increased competition for resources, potential reduction in bespoke services, and dependency on federated systems.	Long queue times, data transfer and curation challenges, and complexity in managing workflows across systems.

Potential User Archetypes

Workshop 1				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Frontline & Applied Health Researchers	Researchers and practitioners in primary care and regional health systems.	Access to broader datasets and compute resources to support care and research.	Security concerns, data governance complexity, and risks of data misuse.	Barriers to access, lack of expertise, and dependency on intermediaries.
Education & Public Engagement Users	Teachers, students, and public sector users interested in engaging with research systems.	Access to shared datasets, tools, and learning opportunities.	Limited influence on system direction and risk of being under-represented.	Lack of knowledge, unclear use cases, and difficulty accessing relevant resources.
Emerging Digital & Interdisciplinary Researchers	Researchers beginning to engage with HPC or working across disciplines (e.g., biosciences).	Upskilling opportunities, access to tools, and ability to enhance research capabilities.	Risk of losing competitive advantage or being "scooped," and a reliance on unfamiliar systems.	Not knowing what's available, difficulty identifying entry points, and navigating systems.
Applied & Industry-Linked Researchers	Researchers or organisations exploring practical applications of infrastructure (including industry-adjacent work).	Access to compute capacity, improved workflows, and potential for innovation.	Significant retraining requirements, financial costs, and disruption to existing practices.	Unclear value proposition, onboarding challenges, and difficulty integrating systems.
Academic & Specialist Users Expanding Scope	Researchers with some experience but looking to expand into new data or systems.	Access to additional datasets, tools, and collaborative opportunities.	Increased complexity, reliance on systems, and potential misalignment with existing workflows.	Understanding system capabilities, accessing appropriate resources, and navigating requirements.

Workshop 2				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Emerging Computational Users	Researchers with access to datasets but limited experience using federated or HPC systems.	Ability to share work, access compute resources, and adopt more advanced research methods.	Learning curve associated with new systems and workflows.	Limited awareness of available infrastructure and difficulty navigating systems.
Collaborative & Cross-Institution Researchers	Researchers seeking to collaborate across institutions or disciplines, including those needing shared compute or data.	Access to shared resources, simplified collaboration, and improved research efficiency.	Time and effort required to integrate new systems into existing workflows.	Difficulty discovering resources, fragmented access, and inconsistent user experiences.
Applied & Industry-Adjacent Researchers	Researchers or practitioners looking to apply computational tools (e.g. AI) to real-world problems.	Access to compute systems, datasets, and tools that support innovation and application.	Concerns about system complexity, cost, and alignment with existing workflows.	Navigating complex systems, lack of support, and unclear pathways to access.
Research Service &	Organisations providing infrastructure, data services, or	Opportunities to standardise services,	Financial and organisational costs	Integration with legacy systems,

Platform Providers	technical support to research communities.	improve user experience, and expand reach.	of adopting federated systems, and the need to retrain staff.	coordination challenges, and unclear governance models.
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Workshop 3				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Cross-Disciplinary Researchers	Researchers working across domains or applying methods from one field to another.	Easier pathways to access resources, more training opportunities, and exposure to broader datasets.	Risk of too many choices, lack of tailored support, and reliance on unfamiliar systems.	Difficulty understanding how to access systems, barriers to entry, and lack of clear guidance.
Applied & Industry-Adjacent Researchers	SMEs, applied researchers, and industry collaborators exploring access to compute and data resources.	Access to innovation support, training, and resources to develop new products and services.	Less bespoke support, less relevant training, and difficulty aligning systems with business needs.	Navigating systems, understanding value, and integrating into existing workflows.
Humanities & Social Science Researchers	Researchers in humanities and social sciences who are beginning to engage with digital tools and datasets.	Access to data, discovery tools, and collaboration opportunities across disciplines.	Over-reliance on unfamiliar systems and loss of established research practices.	Trust in data and processes, accessibility of systems, and difficulty understanding relevance.
Early Career & Emerging Researchers	PhD students and early-career researchers exploring federated infrastructure for the first time.	Access to training, shared tools, and visibility of what others are doing (data discovery).	Less tailored training, risk of overwhelm, and reduced bespoke support.	Lack of awareness, unclear entry points, barriers to access, and difficulty understanding system value.

Inactive User Archetypes

Workshop 1				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Commercial & Start-up Organisations	Start-ups and companies not fully aligned with academic or clinical systems.	Access to research data, faster innovation cycles, and improved collaboration opportunities.	Risk aversion due to data governance, cultural mismatch, and perceived lack of alignment with academic systems.	Difficulty accessing systems, lack of clear pathways, and misalignment with business needs.
Private Sector & Cloud-Dependent Organisations	Private companies relying on cloud services or operating outside federated systems.	Access to low-cost or shared resources and potential collaboration opportunities.	Concerns about value vs private cloud, loss of control, and unclear benefits.	Bureaucracy, trust in single providers, and uncertainty about federation advantages.
Non-HPC & Low-Engagement Researchers	Researchers in disciplines that do not typically use HPC or advanced infrastructure.	Opportunity to access new tools and capabilities if engaged.	Fear of change, lack of relevance, and perceived complexity.	Low awareness, skills gaps, and uncertainty about benefits.
Financial & Risk-Sensitive Organisations	Financial services and organisations with strong governance and privacy requirements.	Potential access to data and analytical tools.	Data privacy concerns, consent issues, and loss of competitive advantage.	Long-term planning challenges, regulatory constraints, and difficulty aligning with fast-moving systems.
Voluntary Sector &	Voluntary/community sector organisations and users with	Access to data, tools, and opportunities for skill development.	Risk of exclusion, lack of resources, and	Difficulty accessing systems, lack of skills/training, and

Access-Limited Users	limited access to infrastructure.		barriers to participation.	limited awareness of opportunities.
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Workshop 2				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Commercial & Industry Organisations	Private companies and start-ups that could benefit from research infrastructure but are not currently engaged.	Access to datasets and analytical capabilities to support innovation.	Concerns around intellectual property, data ownership, and competitive advantage.	Perception of slow, bureaucratic access processes and unclear value proposition.
Financial & Regulated Sector Users	Financial service providers and organisations operating under strict regulatory requirements.	Opportunities to leverage advanced analytics and modelling capabilities.	Privacy, compliance, and trust concerns related to data sharing.	Uncertainty around governance, compliance requirements, and system suitability.
Public & Community Sector Organisations	Voluntary, community, and public sector organisations with potential to use research data.	Access to data and analytical tools to support decision-making and social impact.	Limited technical capacity and resources to adopt new systems.	Lack of awareness, accessibility challenges, and difficulty navigating complex systems.
Disengaged or Excluded Users	Users or organisations unaware of, excluded from, or unable to access federated systems.	Potential inclusion in research ecosystems and access to previously unavailable resources.	Risk of being overwhelmed by complexity and lack of tailored support.	Low awareness, unclear entry points, and barriers to engagement with federated infrastructure.

Workshop 3				
Archetype	Who They Are	Gains from Federation	Potential Losses	Current Frustrations
Public Sector & Service Organisations	Public services and healthcare practitioners who could benefit from data but are not actively engaged.	Access to advanced analysis tools, skills, and data-driven insights.	Risk of increased barriers to access and reduced control over data use.	Skills gaps, unclear value, and difficulty accessing usable data.
Low-Engagement Organisations	Organisations aware of federation but not actively participating due to limited perceived value.	Potential access to data services and improved awareness of available resources.	Uncertainty about benefits and effort required to engage.	Lack of awareness, low discoverability of services, and unclear entry points.
Cultural & Small Data Holders	Small museums, libraries, and organisations with valuable but underutilised datasets.	Opportunities to share, access, and analyse collections; increased visibility.	Limited influence over systems, resource constraints, and lack of control.	Budget limitations, lack of standards, and insufficient support for participation.
Non-Participants / Sceptical Users	Individuals or organisations who do not see value in federation or data reuse (including some private sector actors).	Potential access to datasets, insights, and collaboration opportunities.	Concerns about loss of control, unclear ROI, and cultural resistance.	Lack of trust, not knowing where to start, and limited awareness of benefits.

Appendix B – Scenario Sub-archetypes

The future landscape archetypes were identified by synthesising insights across all 60 scenarios generated within the workshops. Each archetype contains distinct sub-archetypes, identified as clusters of related scenarios that emerged from the workshop discussions. These are presented below, each with a brief overview and an indication of which workshops contributed the underlying scenarios. Where one sub-archetype appeared more frequently than others, this is also noted.

Future Scenario Landscape A sub-archetypes

Platform Monoculture (WS1 and WS3)

Research infrastructures become shaped by vendor ecosystems, AI pipelines, and managed compute platforms. Compatibility with dominant platforms increasingly defines what research is feasible.

National Compute Authority (Most common; Identified WS1 and WS2 participants)

Infrastructure is coordinated strategically through national programmes and mission-led investment. Central governance supports large-scale capability but narrows methodological flexibility.

Future Scenario Landscape B sub-archetypes

Invisible Substrate (WS3, and 1 WS2)

Shared AI models and technical stacks quietly standardise research practices beneath apparently distributed governance.

Standards Commonwealth (WS1 and WS2)

Protocols, schemas, and interoperability frameworks enable collaboration across institutions but gradually align epistemic expectations.

Convergent Network (WS2, WS3, and 1 WS1)

Funding priorities, procurement decisions, and training ecosystems produce convergence over time without explicit coordination.

Future Scenario Landscape C sub-archetypes

Curated Pluralism Regime (Most common; WS1, WS2, WS3)

Central infrastructures support multiple knowledge communities through representation, accreditation, and structured participation pathways.

Framework Pluralism Regime (WS1, WS3, and 1 WS2)

Shared modular infrastructure layers enable diverse approaches to coexist while maintaining interoperability through common connectors and standards.

Future Scenario Landscape D sub-archetypes

Knowledge Bazaar (WS1, and 1 WS2)

Innovation spreads through experimentation and peer adoption rather than central coordination.

Federated Commons (Most common; WS1, WS2, WS3)

Communities maintain autonomy while collaborating through negotiated federation layers and lightweight interoperability agreements.

Fragmented Wildlands (WS3, and 1 WS1)

Plural infrastructures expand without sufficient coordination scaffolding, increasing duplication and reducing system coherence.

Appendix C – Summary of Exercise 3 Windtunnelling Users groups vs Scenarios

Scenario Landscape A's consequences on User Archetypes

Active Users	<p>Strengthens the position of already engaged users through coordination and standardisation, but reduces their flexibility, innovation space, and control over tools, workflows, and data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Innovation space narrows significantly• Governance becomes stronger but more restrictive• Data control and platform dependence become major concerns• Compliance introduces hidden workflow costs• Infrastructure centralisation risks reducing ecosystem diversity• Policy direction becomes a stronger shaping force
Potential Users	<p>Infrastructure participation easier to understand and navigate for potential users, but introduces stronger conditions for entry and increases reliance on central systems that may not reflect all community needs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation pathways become clearer, but more conditional• Participation becomes more binary (in or out)• Infrastructure clarity improves, but flexibility decreases• Governance and data rules shape willingness to participate• Smaller organisations and non-prioritised communities risk exclusion• Standardisation improves onboarding but increases dependence on central systems• Education pathways benefit, but institutional priorities shape inclusion
Inactive Users	<p>More predictable and policy-aligned infrastructure environment that supports accountability and capability-building, but increases reliance on government direction and advantages larger organisations over smaller or less aligned participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• A controlled infrastructure environment is seen as reassuring but restrictive• Policy direction becomes the dominant shaping force• Large organisations gain advantage over smaller ones• Institutional alignment becomes a prerequisite for engagement• Education pipelines strengthen long-term capability• Some communities remain excluded despite lower technical barriers• Scenario A introduces trade-offs between protection and openness

Scenario Landscape B's consequences on User Archetypes

Active Users	<p>More plural and specialist-led infrastructure environment that increases provider choice, domain control, and opportunities for competition, but reduces interoperability, coordination efficiency, and consistency across the ecosystem.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Domain specialists gain more control over infrastructure direction• Provider diversity increases and monopoly risks decrease• Interoperability becomes harder to maintain• Competition increases across the infrastructure landscape• Governance supports high-trust and sensitive data environments• Access improves in some ways but becomes more fragmented overall• Vendor lock-in risks persist despite increased provider diversity
Potential Users	<p>Enabling step-by-step entry into infrastructure through local and specialised services, increasing choice and resilience but making participation harder to navigate and uneven across domains without strong interoperability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Participation pathways become more gradual and locally accessible• Provider diversity increases choice, but creates navigation challenges• Interoperability becomes a critical condition for success• Distributed governance increases resilience and trust• Smaller organisations and local actors gain participation opportunities• Representation gaps remain for diverse or resource-poor communities• Standardisation supports mobility, but may constrain diversity
Inactive Users	<p>Distributed infrastructure environment that improves accountability, investment readiness, and service continuity through provider plurality, while increasing coordination complexity and raising participation barriers for organisations without clear entry pathways or aligned services.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Distributed governance strengthens accountability and investment readiness• Provider plurality increases resilience but raises security concerns• Choice increases, but navigation complexity becomes a barrier• Participation depends strongly on whether services exist for specific communities• Representation gaps persist for emerging and inactive communities• Entry barriers increase due to platform diversity• Distributed infrastructure supports continuity and reduces disruption risk

Scenario Landscape C's consequences on User Archetypes

Active Users	<p>A heterogeneous but governance-layered infrastructure environment that supports experimentation, collaboration across systems, and specialist autonomy, while increasing coordination effort, technical workload, and risks of reduced experimentation as systems scale.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Diversity of tools and approaches enables innovation but complicates coordination• Governance provides clarity while shaping research boundaries• Convergence mechanisms support cross-system collaboration• Experimentation space narrows as systems scale• Technical effort increases for established users• Standards and consistency support adoption pathways• Participation risks emerge for smaller or less-visible research teams
Potential Users	<p>A diverse and automation-supported infrastructure environment that improves collaboration through shared vocabularies and cross-disciplinary access, while making participation increasingly dependent on digital literacy, trust in governance structures, and alignment with standardised processes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Diversity increases participation flexibility but makes coordination harder• Standardisation supports collaboration through shared language and automation• Digital literacy becomes a critical participation condition• Cross-disciplinary access becomes a key innovation pathway• Governance simplifies access but shapes participation conditions• Standardisation creates tensions with local practices and education pathways• Trust conditions shape willingness to engage with federated infrastructures
Inactive Users	<p>A governance-coordinated but diverse infrastructure environment that supports institutional mobility, training pathways, and multiple adoption routes, while continuing to require active representation mechanisms and technical support capacity to ensure smaller and emerging communities can participate effectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Governance layers enable diversity across infrastructures• Upskilling and training opportunities increase across services• Multiple entry pathways improve accessibility• Mobility between institutions becomes easier• Representation risks remain for smaller research communities• Established communities benefit but technical support demands increase

Scenario Landscape D's consequences on User Archetypes

Active Users	<p>A flexible infrastructure environment that supports innovation, resource alignment with research needs, and more democratic participation for active users, while increasing interoperability requirements, negotiation effort, and competition for shared infrastructure capacity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Flexibility and innovation increase for established users• Technical compatibility becomes a critical condition for collaboration• Coordination overhead increases through negotiation and mediation layers• Resource competition increases across active users• Industry influence increases through infrastructure funding relationships• Risks of fragmentation (“silo-fication”) remain present• Participation becomes more active but requires greater technical effort
Potential Users	<p>A high-choice but complex federated infrastructure environment that enables users to select services aligned with their needs, while increasing participation uncertainty, literacy requirements, and dependence on guidance frameworks to support collaboration and trusted engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Service choice increases but navigation becomes difficult• Participation depends strongly on digital literacy and support capacity• Collaboration becomes harder without shared guidance frameworks• Resource competition increases across user communities• Reliability and accountability become uncertain in distributed environments• Trust conditions shape willingness to federate data and participate• Reflects familiar participation dynamics similar to the current landscape
Inactive Users	<p>A plural and community-driven infrastructure environment that allows organisations to shape participation around their needs and identify aligned providers, while increasing uncertainty about accountability, vocabulary alignment across domains, and participation pathways for smaller communities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Governance clarity and accountability become major participation concerns• Infrastructure plurality increases flexibility but makes engagement harder to navigate• Vocabulary fragmentation creates communication and participation barriers• Learning and capability development become major participation conditions• Industry plays a stronger role in sustaining infrastructure ecosystems• Smaller communities face greater exposure in fragmented environments• Community proximity improves participation opportunities where alignment exists

Insights from across **all scenarios** that effect **each User Archetype**

Active Users

- innovation depends on balancing coordination with flexibility
- interoperability is essential for collaboration at scale
- governance shapes both access and methodological autonomy
- provider diversity improves resilience but increases coordination effort
- distributed systems increase competition for shared resources
- platform dependence and vendor lock-in remain ongoing concerns
- infrastructure diversity increases technical workload
- specialist infrastructures support communities but risk ecosystem fragmentation

Potential Users

- clear entry pathways determine whether participation is possible
- greater provider choice increases opportunity but complicates navigation
- governance and data rules shape willingness to participate
- digital literacy and onboarding support are essential participation conditions
- standardisation supports collaboration but may reduce flexibility
- smaller organisations remain at risk of exclusion without targeted support
- interoperability is critical in distributed infrastructure environments
- local and education-based entry points support gradual engagement

Inactive Users

- governance clarity determines whether participation feels possible
- institutional alignment matters more than technical access
- smaller and emerging communities remain at risk of exclusion
- skills pipelines and capability-building shape long-term participation
- greater provider choice increases flexibility but also complexity
- policy direction strongly shapes participation expectations
- representation in governance is essential for engagement
- stability and continuity matter more than optimisation or experimentation